

IHI 101112022 - iCARE4CVD

INDIVIDUALISED CARE FROM EARLY RISK
OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE TO
ESTABLISHED HEART FAILURE

WP2 – Federated Data Management

D2.1 Federated Data analysis Architecture – Part 1

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable focuses on reporting on the Federated Data Infrastructure for iCARE4CVD. The deliverable reports on the work performed within the first six months of the project. In this document we describe the three-layered architecture. We describe each layer in terms of components and how they connect to one another. In particular, we explain the 3 layers in terms of the three main components: 1. the Cohort Explorer – a tool for exploring and mapping the data into the iCARE4CVD platform: 2. The blockchain monitoring – a tool to enable data owners to manage their own cohorts and 3. Data clean rooms – offered by the Decentriq platform where the data are stored under the control of data owners and are analysed by researchers in respect to data sharing agreements.

This deliverable will be updated as further developments and updates are performed in the platform, however, in this document we also highlight the overall vision for the platform and distinguish between the implemented parts and those that are to be further developed as the project continues.

2 Introduction

Our architecture has three layers, each designed to protect patient data privacy while enabling flexible analysis (Fig. 1). The Cohort explorer UI based on knowledge graphs provides a unified interface for exploring cohorts on a meta-data level, making it easy for analysts to discover data. In the analysis layer, LUCE Blockchain [8] platform handles data permissions and holds data sharing agreements. Decentriq Data Clean Rooms ensures secure data analysis while enabling regulatory compliance. Our architecture enables researchers to analyse data efficiently and securely while allowing partners providing data to maintain control over processing of such data and preserving patient privacy.

Fig 1. Technical Architecture Components

1. In the Cohort Explorer, metadata is mapped into a common ontology and made available to the researchers for identifying relevant cohorts (no patient data, only meta-data).
2. Data sharing parameters are defined in the blockchain platform, ensuring data governance.
3. Encrypted data can be analysed while remaining fully under the data owners' control. For a deeper dive on what this means see the DCR Data Protection whitepaper [\[6\]](#), [\[7\]](#)

From a user experience, there are two main types of users: data owners (also known as data custodians or data providers) and researchers (also known as data requesters or data analysts). In general, users of iCARE4CVD go through the following process which is also illustrated in Fig 2:

1. Users connect to the cohort explorer UI and create an account
2. If they are data owners, they upload their data dictionary (metadata). The cohort explorer, help data owners to complete the mapping into a knowledge graph.
3. Users access the Decentriq environment where they get the encryption toolkit to connect their data to a Data Clean Room
4. Researchers (data analyst), can form questions in the cohort explorer and analyse encrypted data in Data Clean Rooms
5. Data owners approve the analyses.

Fig: 2 High Level Component Interactions in iCARE4CVD

6. Approved results are retrieved without the raw data ever being exposed or compromised.
7. Blockchain keeps an immutable record of all the actions that happen to the data (i.e User X explored the data Y, User X submitted a request for analysis ect).

A technical factsheet of the main components of the architecture and their interactions was sent to all partners. This summary has included it in the Annexes section.

3 Methods

In this section we will provide an overall architecture and will further develop the 3 components of the architecture, namely: the Cohort Explorer/ Knowledge graph: the first ideas behind LUCE blockchain (the detailed version is planned for later updates to this document - V2), and the Data Clean Room Component.

3.1 ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

Fig 3 depicts a detailed general architecture that includes the three layers shown in Fig.2. Three main users are shown to be interacting in the platform: Data owner/provider, Admin and the Researcher/Data Requester. For simplicity we will refer to the users as data owners, admin and researchers. Data owners are asked to complete a data dictionary template prior to engaging with the platform. The data dictionary template was developed as part of WP1 and consist in various fields capturing the variables in the cohort, their description and their representation. For more details, please refer to the deliverables of WP1.

Fig 3: iCARE4CVD General Architecture.

Fig 3 depicts how a data owner, after completing the data dictionary, will interact with the iCARE4CVD platform via the Cohort Explorer. The Cohort Explorer exposes a Frontend to engage with the iCARE4CVD users. Data dictionaries are checked for errors, missing fields or wrong values. The errors of the data dictionary are shown to the user (typically the data owner or the admin). The users can update the data dictionary and come back to upload it to the platform.

Data owners can specify for which research purposes the cohort can be shared. Within the blockchain Layer, a transparent monitoring and data management process is established. If needed, and in accordance with the consent agreement, data owners can limit researchers to perform questions within the scope of one disease. Furthermore, cohort access can be limited by geographically (i.e only researchers within the EU). The blockchain layer can enforce these mechanisms dynamically. The cohort explorer interacts with the blockchain layer, prior to enabling the researcher to access the cohorts in the Decentriq Data Clean Room.

Finally, cohorts will be uploaded by the data owner in the data clean room (DCR). The researcher selects the cohorts in the cohort explorer. The cohort explorer will send the information about which variables of the cohorts the researcher would like to access. The researcher can then interact in the DCR to. Specify what they would like to do, to create the analytical scripts and request permissions to run them.

In the following sections we further explain each layer in more details.

3.2 LAYER 1: COHORT EXPLORER

3.2.1 The Cohort Explorer

The Cohort Explorer provides three main functionalities: exploring cohorts, querying cohorts and merging cohorts. At the time of reporting, we have developed the first part: cohort exploration as well as some aspects of querying cohorts. This layer (shown in purple in Fig. 3) only handles metadata (descriptions of the cohorts and/or datasets as provided by the users of the platform).

In Fig 3, we show the **Cohort Explorer Frontend**. This is the main interface of iCARE4CVD. Via this interface, users of iCARE4CVD connect and can see summary data from the cohorts as they are described by data owners.

The **Cohort Explorer API** (also known as the back end) mediates the interactions between the users and the system. It ensures that users are authenticated at log-in, it receives Data Dictionaries which then are displayed in the Cohort Explorer Frontend. The cohort explorer API supports the following:

- **User log-in and authentication:** Users of iCARE4CVD login with their Decentriq account (OAuth based authentication). Only accounts with the required permissions will be able to access the platform. Members of the iCare4CVD project need to contact Decentriq to request an account prior to being able to interact with the platform. In technical terms, once the user is logged in through the (Decentriq) OAuth provider, the backend generates an encrypted JASON Web Token (JWT) [9], which is passed to the frontend using HTTP-only cookies.
- **Uploading and storing metadata:** Users are provided with a data dictionary. Such data dictionary is aimed at capturing metadata of the various cohorts/datasets. To date, the assumption is that cohorts are organized in one table (i.e. one csv file), this is in line with the information collected by the iCARE4CVD partners. The Cohort Explorer API performs checks on the data dictionary to ensure that the data dictionaries are filled in and do not contain errors.
- **Mapping of the cohort variables.** Currently, the mapping is manually performed. An integration to ATHENA OHDSI [10], helps the identification of the main concepts. A ranking mechanism supports the user (admin or data owner) to identify to which IDs are most used and by which other cohorts. Consistency in mapping will be achieved in later stages of the project by: i) Fixing the IDs for common variables; ii). Enabling admin mapping; iii) Deploying AI tools to automate mappings as much as possible; iv) Enabling key data scientists in the project to review existing mappings.
- **Storing the mappings** into a structured knowledge graph. The identified mappings are stored into a triple store. As more cohorts are incorporated in iCARE4CVD, we identify new concepts and include them as part of the ontology of the knowledge graph. We use OMOP [1] as a basis for defining such ontology but extend when needed with other concepts (i.e from SNOMED, LOINC). The current ontology is very basic. As more cohort data are described within the system, the ontology will evolve. In the following section we expand our discussion with more information on the semantic model of iCARE4CVD.
- **Querying Cohorts:** Cohorts that are described (with the data dictionaries) in the system, can be explored by researchers. Via the cohort explorer frontend, users can view the cohorts. A simple filtering has already been implemented to filter cohorts by type or by specific variables. In the future, more complex queries will be supported.
- **Merging cohorts:** This is a functionality that it is currently not available in the cohort explorer. Some level of merging of cohorts will be possible once, the ontology and the mapping of cohorts has been performed. The merging will be possible only after the researcher has been granted access (via the blockchain layer) to all the cohorts that are requested to be merged.
- **Request Access to data:** Via the cohort explorer, users can add the cohorts of interest and request access to the data in a data clean room. The architecture anticipates, a request to access each relevant cohort to be recorded in the blockchain. Should the purpose of study be in-line with the data collection purposes, then the permissions can be granted. A structure of the query (the variables that need to be

accessed in each cohort) is sent to the data clean room which handles the rest of the interactions between the researcher and the iCARE4CVD platform.

3.2.2 OMOP Semantic Model: Ontology

Formal ontologies have become a mainstay in the codification of medical knowledge, enabling not only reasoned data analysis but also the reuse and sharing of data across systems. Simultaneously, relational database models like the OMOP Common Data Model [13] have been recognized for their practicality in organizing and standardizing EHR data. Recent studies suggest that OMOP's content coverage surpasses that of other common data models, demonstrating its effectiveness in the field.

Ontology Model Overview: The ontology, presented in Fig 4 is constructed with the explicit intent to serve as an integrative semantic framework for the healthcare domain, particularly accentuating the centrality of patient care. The model is architected to establish and explicate the relational nexus among patients, their medical conditions, medications exposures, procedural interventions, and an array of health-related measurements. It aims to harmonize with extant data models, particularly the OMOP Common Data Model [1], ensuring the comprehensive encapsulation of healthcare concepts. We have considered existing established ontologies to judiciously incorporate entities and relationships, notably the Semantic Science Integrated Ontology (SIO) [3], which provides standardized taxonomy and common semantic foundation. This alignment with pre-existing ontological constructs not only ensures semantic congruity but also enhances the model's utility in facilitating data exchange and interoperability across diverse healthcare systems and applications. It is poised to serve as a pivotal tool in the advancement of semantic knowledge discovery within the ICARE4CVD for cardiovascular diseases system.

Rationale Behind the Model Design: The ontology is strategically designed to address the complexities of healthcare data representation, ensuring that individuals, their health conditions, interventions, and related healthcare interactions to be distinctly and comprehensively modelled. Below is the description of ontology components shown in Fig.4:

- **Entity:** Within the realm of patient studies, a multitude of entities can be conceptualized to encapsulate the various aspects of the healthcare domain. These include, but are not limited to, individuals (patients), medical devices, pharmaceuticals, and model organisms used in research. Moreover, the outcomes or results derived from healthcare processes also constitute entities. These encompass information content entities, which hold data such as medical records and test results; diagnostic opinions, which represent the interpretive conclusions drawn by healthcare professionals; and temporal entities, which serve to denote specific periods or intervals pertinent to patient care, such as the duration of treatment or observation. Collectively, these entities form a comprehensive network of interrelated data points essential for a robust representation of patient studies and healthcare interactions.
- **Attribute:** Attributes describe properties or characteristics of entities. They are connected to entities through the **sio:has_attribute** relationship. These attributes can be quantifier and qualitative attributes. Examples include blood pressure, date of birth, date of death, status, and answers to specific questions.
- **Role:** This defines the function or position that an entity can have in a certain context. Here, the roles are patient and medical practitioner. Roles are associated with entities through the **sio:has_role** relationship.
- **Process:** A series of actions or steps taken to achieve a particular end. In a medical context, this could be a diagnostic procedure or treatment plan e.g. lab tests, imaging or surgical interventions. The processes related to drugs such as prescription process and administration process can also be represented through process entity. Processes have outputs, which are indicated by the **sio:has_output** relationship.
- **Identifier:** Unique symbols or codes assigned to entities to identify them without ambiguity. In healthcare, this is crucial for patient identification while maintaining privacy. An example given is pseudonym Patient-ID or unique identification of concept in controlled vocabularies e.g. SNOMED, LOINC etc.
- **Relationships:**
 - The relationship between entities can be represented through various predicates such as **sio:has_attribute** Links entities to their attributes such as patient has_gender female,

- **sio:has_role:** links entities to the roles they can perform at specific point in time. An example can be person who is medical practioner but has a role of patient when ill.
- **sio:is_realised_in:** connects roles to processes, indicating the context in which a role is executed. It represents the semantic context in which an entity with specific role in involved in a process such as ‘blood pressure measurement record of patient xyz’ is process with output in information content entity (value of measurement, unit of measurement) in which role of xyz is patient.
- **sio:denotes:** Associates identifiers with entities they identify. **sio:refers_to:** Specifies the target of a reference, such as an attribute referring to an entity. **sio:has_output:** Connects a process to its result or output, which is also an entity.

Fig: 4 Semantic Model based on OMOP Data Elements

This work is being constantly expanded and evolved as more data dictionaries and cohorts are made available. We further explain our future plans in section 5.

3.2 LAYER 2: LUCE BLOCKCHAIN MODEL

This layer is only concerned with data access permissions. No cohort or patient data are recorded in the blockchain layer. This layer records the fact that a cohort is shared by a specific organisation and can be accessed by others under specific conditions. Such concisions describe what sort of research questions can be performed on a cohort. In this layer, we can manage these permissions to create a broad transparency level on how the cohorts are used by other organisations. In the following we describe all these aspects in more detail:

3.2.1 LUCE Blockchain

License Accountability and Compliance Enhancement (LUCE) [8] is a blockchain-based platform designed for transparent data sharing and its reuse, thereby facilitating accountability and compliance inherently. The core features of LUCE primarily encompass: (a) managing licensing terms associated with a cohort/dataset, (b)

handling the reuse purpose and user consent in a flexible manner, and (c) ensuring compliance with rights to access, rectification, and data erasure.

LUCE uses a blockchain network to establish a shared and transparent ledger of who shares which data, under which terms and who accesses them and for which purpose. As in any blockchain, it relies on the concept of valid transactions to capture what happens to the data. It also includes smart contracts as executable rules that must be followed when interacting with the system. Transactions in iCARE4CVD record actions of users. Before these actions are performed, they are recorded and validated by smart contracts.

In terms of data management, LUCE emphasizes three main steps: sharing data, reusing data, and ensuring compliance with the GDPR's provisions for access, rectification, and erasure. In managing data, LUCE operates under a few assumptions: First, datasets are shared in their entirety without considering dataset integration—meaning the combination of multiple datasets for reuse is not supported. Second, it is assumed that data sharing permissions set by the data owners align with the consent provided by data subjects. Third, personal data is de-identified, with only the data owner being able to link data subjects to their records; notably, data owners and subjects may be the same in cases of personal data sharing.

In Fig. 3 we show 2 main components of LUCE that interact in the iCARE4CVD framework. The **LUCE blockchain API**, used to transact in the blockchain (insert information into the blockchain layer) and the **Data Sharing Monitoring with Smart Contracts** which consist of pre-established data management rules that are specific to each cohort and controlled by the data owners.

Sharing Monitoring with Smart Contracts: In LUCE, each cohort/dataset is associated with a unique smart contract, serving multiple critical functions: Firstly, it manages access rights, as set by the data owners, ensuring data is accessed only under agreed licensing terms through binding agreements between data owners and researchers. Secondly, it offers a mechanism for provenance verification, embedding the dataset's hash within the contract to unambiguously establish ownership and protect against data theft and intellectual property violations. Thirdly, the contract enables an immutable history of dataset access, detailing who accessed the data, the duration, and the purpose, which is pivotal for data subjects' right to information and for auditing compliance with licensing terms.

The LUCE blockchain API: To interact with LUCE, the Cohort Explorer will use the LUCE blockchain API. This API supports actions tailored to each user role – for instance, it allows data owners to register, publish, update, or remove information about the cohort data, facilitating dynamic data management; Researchers (as Data requesters) can request access to cohort data, and periodically affirm license compliance to secure ongoing access rights, thereby simplifying the process of data utilization; Additionally, LUCE introduces several components to maintain a local overview of the platform's state. In particular, a secure data storage component is responsible for the safe access to datasets, requiring valid LUCE tokens for entry. For user authentication and access control, a user registry contract records all registered blockchain addresses, allowing only verified users to engage with the LUCE Blockchain. Data concerning users (data owners or researchers), is securely stored in a local database (LuceDB). This database mirrors the information held in smart contracts—such as dataset hashes, metadata, license types, intended uses, and user access rights—but also serves as a dynamic cache, facilitating access to data without the need to query the blockchain for each interaction, thus ensuring efficient and seamless user experiences on the platform.

The following paragraphs outline what happens in the blockchain when data is shared or accessed. Such functionalities will be carefully integrated at the later stages of the project.

What happens in the LUCE blockchain when Data Owners Share Data?

The data-sharing process begins with data owners uploading the data dictionary in the cohort explorer front-end. This act is sent to the LUCE platform (not the data dictionary). This will prompt the questions for the data

owners on the data re-use terms of the dataset. A smart contract is created encapsulating the link between the data owner, the cohort and the re-use terms of the data. The data owner is recorded in the blockchain with an ID which in blockchain terms is called address. The link between the data owner's name and the address is kept private in the LuceDB. To an external observer, the actions in the system are not identifiable. They can be identified only in the iCARE4CVD platform.

What happens in the LUCE blockchain when Data Requesters Access Data?

Before being able to analyse data in a data clean room, researchers will determine what are their research needs. This for example could be expressed as: *I want to perform disease specific research on heart failure, I will do this in the next 6 months and with a non-profit intension.* Upon selecting the interesting cohorts in the cohort explorer, researchers will request access through the smart contracts of the individual cohorts, This interaction is handled by an interaction between the cohort explorer API and the LUCE API. This step includes a compatibility check between the reuse purpose and the original data as provided by the data owner, facilitated by the smart contract. To this, access is only granted after researchers agree to the licensing terms, with the smart contract subsequently issuing a verification token and access link to the data clean room.

The second step in LUCE's data reuse process is the monitoring of compliance with a dataset's licensing terms, facilitated by an access token. This token, issued by the smart contract once a data requester agrees to the terms and defines their purpose for using the data, enables not only dataset access but also its renewal and deletion when necessary. For those interested in the technical details, this is achieved by incorporating extensions to the ERC-721 standard, the system ensures transparent data ownership and usage rights. The access token's validity is time-bound, demanding renewal through the smart contract based on the researcher's adherence to licensing terms. Failure to comply leads to the denial of token renewal, effectively restricting further access to data.

3.3 LAYER 3: DATA CLEAN ROOMS

The first two layers handle metadata and access control but do not see or store the cohorts or more broadly speaking the health data themselves. The third layer deals with the sensitive data themselves. Due to the sensitivity of health data, instead of using common cloud-based models to enable data analysis, we rely on the Decentriq platform and their notion of data clean room.

Decentriq is a cloud service software platform that provides a unique promise: data can be used for collaboration without being shared, data can only be used for a specific limited purpose, and compliance can be remotely verified. This is true even when the data is used in collaboration with other companies. The original owner retains full control over the data during the entire lifecycle and can prove that it was only used for an explicit and limited purpose. This provides tangible benefits to organizations that use Decentriq's platform:

1. The platform drastically reduces the risk that a researcher mishandles or leaks data.
2. Participants can extend the scope for which they can compliantly process personal data under GDPR and other regulations by eliminating the need to share personal data, reducing the risk of misuse.
3. Participants can collaborate with other Data Owners without having to trust anyone with their data, enabling the joint use of business secrets even between competitors.

To provide these fully verifiable data protection guarantees, Decentriq implements **Confidential Computing**. While data can traditionally be encrypted at-rest (on disk) and in-transit (over network), Confidential Computing also encrypts information in memory while it is in-use. The platform is able to do this with the support of new **trusted execution environment** hardware technologies like Intel Software Guard Extensions [11], AMD Secure Encrypted Virtualization with Secure Nested Paging [12], and other emerging technology.

3.3.1 Data Clean Room Abstraction

Decentriq enables users to collaborate on data with the guarantee that their contributed data sets can only be used for the explicitly specified intended purpose. The platform uses the metaphor of a **Data Clean Room**, a highly controlled environment free from outside influence, to describe a specific act of collaboration.

The key element that ties a clean room together is a data structure called the **Data Clean Room Configuration**. This data structure contains the essential terms of the collaboration:

1. Table Schemas and File Definitions - what data will be included and how it will be structured.
2. Computations - what operations will be performed on the data.
3. User Permissions - who is responsible for contributing data (Data Owner) and who can see the results (Researcher).
4. Authentication Root - The root certificate authority used for user authentication.
5. Attestation Specification - other technical details required to ensure that the configuration is unambiguous and complete. This includes the verification policy for the hardware.

The Data Clean Room Configuration ties these parameters together into a verifiable format which allows each participant to review and understand the scope of collaboration. The Decentriq platform uses cryptographic protocols to indelibly bind these parameters to the code that executes them. This is the “contract” for the collaboration – readable by humans, but enforceable by the platform.

3.3.2 Analysis within DCR

In CARE4CVD, the analysis will take place inside a DCR. The researcher as well as data owners will undergo a series of steps as described below.

Step 1 – Local encryption and upload

Data owners locally encrypt their data with a locally generated encryption key only known to them. The encrypted data is then uploaded to the Decentriq platform. The encryption keys remain with the respective party at this step.

Step 2 – Requesting and approving computations

Once the desired data is provisioned in a DCR, it does not imply unfettered access by the researchers. Instead DCRs operate based on the concept of computation nodes. Different computation nodes have different effects on the data. Researchers never have access to the full data, but only to the results of the computation nodes that must be previously approved by the data owners.

From a data owner’s point of view, the approval is also straightforward. Data owners can see exactly the purpose of the node to be executed, as well as preview the results if they are the only data owner that is affected.

Step 3 – Executing computations and generating results

Once all affected data owners have approved the nodes requested by the researcher, they become a part of the DCR, meaning that they can now be executed on the encrypted data and generate results. The results of the computations are the only output delivered by any DCR to the researcher.

4 Results

The architecture with the main elements described in the previous section has been implemented and it is accessible via the Cohort Explorer Repository <https://github.com/MaastrichtU-IDS/cohort-explorer> . In this repository, installation instructions, the code and all technical documentation can be found.

The current ontology of iCARE4CVD is shared in the following repository. <https://maastrichtu-ids.github.io/cohort-explorer>

As part of the first release and in order to enable testing by the consortium members to interact with the platform, the platform is made accessible via the iCARE4CVD webpage <https://explorer.icare4cvd.eu>

Demo is planned to be provided to partners on April 9th.

4.1 COHORT EXPLORER DEMO

During the first months of the project, the consortium partners provided two cohorts that could be promptly shared within iCARE4CVD framework These two cohorts are used to demonstrate the iCARE4CVD platform:

1. Aachen HF Study and 2. UM CHF dataset. The DEMO involves the following steps:

1. Exploring Cohorts:

The Cohort Explorer shows the overview of the cohorts. A researcher can explore existing cohorts in the system, it can filter them by topology or can search cohorts by variable name. The researcher explores the UM CHF dataset. This cohort has already mapped, and it is ready to be used by researchers.

2. Addition of new Cohorts:

The data owner of the Aachen HF study uploads the Data Dictionary of the cohort. The upload attempt of the data dictionary fails. Two errors are indicated in the cohort explorer front-end (1 wrong datatype, 1 wrong category). The data owner reads the error message, fixes them in the data dictionary, and re-uploads the file. This time the data dictionary is correctly filled in.

3. Mapping a new Cohort:

Using the cohort explorer, the data owner maps the variables to standardised concepts. The variable Gender is mapped and saved into the data dictionary. Similarly, the variable weight is mapped. In both cases the same mapping as the one used in the UM CHF dataset is used.

4. Upload the new cohort in DCR:

The Data owner locally encrypt the Aachen HF study with a locally generated encryption key only known to them. The encrypted data is then uploaded to the Decentriq platform. The encryption keys remain with the respective party at this step.

5. Selecting Cohorts for Analysis:

Using the cohort explorer the researcher can browse the cohorts and their variables. The researcher can:

- Filter by cohorts and by variable. As an example, a search for variables related to "creatinine" is performed. The variable is further explored to show the details.
- Select variables of interest from a cohort. As an example, the researcher selects weight, gender and an outcome variable from Aachen HF and UM CHF cohort.
- Create the DCR with weight, gender and outcome variable in Decentriq. Through the Cohort Explorer Frontend, the user is connected to the DCR created in Decentriq.

6. Creating computations:

The selected data is provisioned in a DCR. The researcher creates computation nodes to combine the two datasets, explore and analyse the data. Once the computation nodes are created, the data owner of the two cohorts (Achen HF and UM CHF) will need to approve them.

7. Analysis and results

Once the data owners approve the nodes requested by the researcher, they become a part of the DCR, meaning that they can now be executed on the encrypted data and generate results. The results of the computations are shown to the researcher.

5 Discussion

5.1 EXTENDING THE COHORT EXPLORER

The first version of the cohort explorer will be tested with end users, and it will be improved based on their feedback. Furthermore, we aim to replace the manual mappings with automatic mappings where possible. For this we are experimenting with Large Language and AI models.

The first iteration of our ontology model has been established to lay the foundational semantic framework for our cardiovascular project. This version delineates a preliminary set of classes and relationships that are pivotal to representing patient data, medical conditions, treatments, and healthcare interactions specific to iCARE4CVD use-cases. Next we will focus on the following steps:

Expansion of Common Data Elements: Our immediate next step is the enrichment of the ontology with common data elements (CDEs) [5] pertinent to cardiovascular health. This includes the incorporation of standardized terms and definitions that capture the nuances of cardiovascular conditions, treatments, diagnostic procedures, and patient outcomes. By integrating these CDEs, we aim to enhance the ontology's specificity and utility within the cardiovascular domain, ensuring it comprehensively captures the data necessary for clinical and research purposes.

Validation of the Ontology Model: Concurrent with the expansion of CDEs, we are initiating a rigorous validation process. This involves subjecting the ontology to a series of tests against real-world cardiovascular datasets to ascertain its accuracy, consistency, and applicability. Through this validation, we seek to identify and rectify any discrepancies, ambiguities, or gaps within the model.

Creation of SHACL Shapes: As part of our quality assurance measures, we will be developing SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language) shapes to enforce data quality and integrity. SHACL shapes will allow us to define constraints to validate RDF data, ensuring that data adheres to the defined schema and that the relationships between entities are semantically consistent. This step is essential to guarantee that our ontology not only accurately represents the cardiovascular domain but also facilitates reliable and robust data integration from diverse sources.

Cohort Merging: Using the ontology, we will be able to identify which transformations must be applied to individual cohort data. These transformations are semi-automated with code whenever possible. For example, if a measurement is in meters and we want to store it in cm, an automatic multiplication by 100 will transform the data in the right format. Shacl-shapes [2] will be used to identify these transformations. These operations will help mapping each variable from the original data dictionary file to a normalized version of the data using concepts of the iCARE4CVD ontology. Examples of such fields to help mapping would be:

- Which OMOP concept/property the variable describes?

- To which OMOP concept should each category match? (autocomplete is based on the previous point)
- What is the formula required to apply on the cell value to get to the right unit? e.g. $x*100$ (When possible, this is deduced from comparing the given unit to the expected unit for the variable concept, as defined in the ontology. When this is not possible, human intervention is needed to fix it in the mapping)
- Remove/delete columns that are not necessary

From the mapping in the Cohort Explorer, a python script is generated to convert the original data to the normalized version for iCARE4CVD.

For example:

1. `df.rename("wrong_column_name", "right_column_name")`
2. `df["variable_with_wrong_unit"].apply(lambda x: x * 100)`
3. `df.drop("unnecessary_column")`

When the data is shared in the Maastricht University server (see section 7 for details), this file is used to normalise the data before storing them within the Data Clean Room. When the data owner is not sharing the data at the Maastricht University Servers, they can export the file, run it locally on their data, to obtain a normalized version of the data. They will also be able to load these normalized data into the data clean room.

Such an approach allows us to:

- Quickly explore the structure of the original cohort data
- Provide basic mapping functions actionable by the data owners themselves
- Enables data scientists to better understand the cohorts
- Flag edge cases during the mapping process by the data owner, then the python code required to fix the edge cases can be manually added to the normalization script later
- Use modern tools (text embeddings + similarity search on the ontology concepts to automatically pre-populate as much as possible the mapping fields)

Dynamic Model: As we refine the ontology, our goal is to achieve a dynamic model that can evolve with the advancements in cardiovascular medicine. This involves continuous collaboration with domain experts, incorporation of feedback from end-users, and adherence to emerging standards in healthcare data exchange. Additionally, we plan to enable the ontology to support advanced analytics and machine learning algorithms, thereby contributing to predictive and prescriptive analytics in cardiovascular care.

Stakeholder Engagement: Throughout the development process, we are aiming to engage with a range of stakeholders, including ontology experts and health care specialists within project to ensure the ontology aligns with the practical needs and expectations of its users. By adopting an iterative and collaborative approach, we are committed to delivering an ontology model that is not only scientifically robust but also pragmatically valuable in the real-world setting of cardiovascular health management.

5.2 EXTENDING THE LUCE BLOCKCHAIN

LUCE's architecture is designed to support a nuanced embodiment of consent logic that goes beyond basic binary logic, offering a robust framework that recognizes the complexities inherent in establishing data consent in real-world applications. For instance, the system incorporates ICD-10 code system to document the disease for which the data cohort can be further re-used. The ICD-10 system is divided into 26 main categories, with each category encompassing up to 99 diseases that can capture data re-use into a dynamic consent management.

More in detail, in order to encode data sharing preferences within a smart consent framework, LUCE will support the expression of complex consent elements such as: This cohort can be shared for diabetes research only, to researchers that operate in the European union and for nonprofit purposes.

In order to capture these requirements, we will utilize a mapping that ties elements of the consent (such as the disease code) to a distinct position in a vector. For example, when capturing the permission to use the data for diabetes research, a vector is used. This vector is set to 1 at a position to signify that explicit consent is given the associated ICD-10 code for diabetes, and 0 to indicates the absence of consent for other diseases (See Fig. 6). This bit-level precision enables LUCE to capture the granular consent preferences of data owners regarding a wide array of diseases. To adjudicate access to data, the system conducts a bitwise AND operation between the disease code provided by the data owner and the one indicated by the researcher. The outcome of this operation is crucial in determining whether the researcher can be granted access to the data. A match between the result and the researcher's disease code means that the researcher's needs align with the consents provided by the data owner, thus granting them access to the data.

Fig 6: A Simplified Illustration of Data Consent Matching in LUCE

In Fig. 6, we illustrate a binary sequence for the data owner (denoted as provider). Their consent includes many conditions therefore it is predominantly composed of 1s, with the exception of some 0s, including the very first bit. Furthermore, when the researcher's sequence is presented (in the figure denoted as the requester), it is apparent they are seeking access to several disease codes, as indicated by the 1s in their sequence. The smart contract processes the access request by executing a bitwise AND operation. Given the starting 0 in both sequences, the result also starts with a 0, maintaining the integrity of the consent (for example if the first position is referring to heart failure, access to analyse data for heart failure will not be granted to the researcher. In fact, the result sequence will only have 1s in positions where both the provider's consent and the requester's access request match—these are the disease codes the requester is authorized to access. Through this approach, LUCE ensures that data sharing is conducted with explicit consent, respecting both the individual's preferences and the data governance policies of providers. Similar approaches are created to determine geographical access – for example to determine if a researcher from the Netherlands can access data if they aim to analyse the cohort for diabetes research.

To understand the consent logic more formally, we define a set of variables representing the various conditions that must be evaluated for consent:

- P_i : a set of propositions representing the data owner's consent conditions, where i ranges over all primary categories (e.g., open to general research, open to disease specific research, ect).
- S_j : a set of propositions representing the data researcher's purpose statements, where j ranges over all possible purposes (e.g., use for fundamental bio research, use for genetics research).
- R_k : A set of propositions representing additional requirements and restrictions, where k ranges over all additional consent requirements (e.g., geographic restrictions, non-profit use only).

Given these, access is granted if and only if, for all consent conditions P_i , there exists at least one corresponding purpose statement S_j that is true, and all additional requirements R_k are also satisfied. This can be expressed as:

$$\text{AccessGranted} \leftrightarrow \bigwedge_i \left(P_i \rightarrow \bigvee_j S_j \right) \wedge \bigwedge_k R_k$$

Let's understand this with an example:

- P_1 : Data is open to general research.
- S_1 : Researcher intends to use the data for fundamental bio research.
- R_1 : The research must be non-profit.
- R_2 : The research requires geographic restriction compliance.

Now, assuming the data powner has consented to the data being open for general research ($P_1 = \text{True}$) and has specified that the research must be non-profit ($R_1 = \text{True}$) and comply with geographic restrictions ($R_2 = \text{True}$), we can evaluate whether a researcher whose purpose is fundamental bio research ($S_1 = \text{True}$) and meets both R_1 and R_2 is granted access: $\text{AccessGranted} \leftrightarrow (P_1 \rightarrow S_1) \wedge R_1 \wedge R_2$. Given P_1 , S_1 , R_1 , and R_2 are all true, that is: $\text{AccessGranted} \leftrightarrow \text{True} \rightarrow \text{True} \wedge \text{True} \wedge \text{True} = \text{True}$; in this scenario, the researcher would be granted access to the data since all the conditions have been met.

This work will be further extended to include permissions on the analysis that can be performed in the DCRs.

5.3 IMPROVING ANALYSIS IN DATA CLEAN ROOMS

Data clean rooms provide a secure environment where researchers can access and analyze sensitive data without compromising privacy or security. By implementing strict controls and protocols, such as anonymization techniques and access controls, clean rooms ensure that individual privacy is protected while enabling diverse research workflows.

Researchers can conduct exploratory data analysis within clean rooms, accessing a wide range of data points while adhering to privacy regulations. Through carefully designed workflows and data governance frameworks, clean rooms allow researchers to explore data sets without risk of exposing sensitive information.

There is an inherent disconnect between the data custodians' need to protect patient privacy, and researchers wanting flexibility and access to as much data as possible. Therefore, through careful balance between flexibility, privacy and security, several aspects of the workflow for both parties will evolve with the course of the project. Such as:

1. **Getting access to data samples for script development:** Researchers have expressed the wish to have access to underlying data and be able to see such datasets, in order to develop their data analysis scripts. As this is not possible, due to privacy and security concerns by many data custodians, there are different ways in which Decentriq has enabled researchers to explore the data in a compliant way. For example, synthetic data generation is performed by the DCR on existing datasets. However, there is a concern for privacy with datasets that contain many variables belonging to very few people. Moreover, researchers have expressed the wishes to have "shuffled data", which cannot be considered anonymous and is easily traceable to the individual patient. With the course of the project, we will assess the level of privacy and security required by GDPR and individual data custodians and provide features to enable more exploratory data analysis within these constraints.

2. **Dynamic consent management:** Currently data owners need to accept and or reject each computational request on the data. In future developments, the blockchain layer can be integrated to further simplify the management of consent based on pre-established rules by the data owner.
3. **Improving the API functionalities of DECENTRIQ platform:** The interaction between the cohort explorer and the DCR is performed from the Cohort Explorer API to the Decentriq API. Further improvements to the Decentriq API may be needed to bring it up-to date to the functionalities that the Decentriq Platform offers within its own front-end platform.

6 Conclusion

This is a first draft work laying down the foundations of the Architecture for iCARE4CVD. In this work we presented a 3 layered architecture, the main components and how they interrelate with one another to create the overall data federation. We made it clear which components are already there and which ones need further work and will be updated as we further work on improving this platform.

7 Repository for primary data

The default repository for the data will be within the DCRs. In DCR, confidential computing guarantees that data are fully controlled by the data owner. The permissions are further enforced by the blockchain layer. The researcher will request access to analyse the data without downloading it or making copies of the data. Data will stay encrypted at all times, unless other agreements are made between the data owner and the researcher.

Several partners of iCARE4CVD have expressed a preference for transferring data to a Maastricht University server. Such data transfer will also be highly beneficial to the project itself as, it can support mapping and knowledge graph creation and it can speed up data analysis for WP5.

To this extend, the same architecture that we described in the sections above remains in place. When data owners are ready to provide the data, and the data sharing agreements are in place, they can upload both the data dictionary and the data via the Cohort Explorer Frontend.

Once this is done, the data is transferred to the UM server. In order to keep focus on the development of the federated platform, the UM server does not offer data analysis capabilities. No access to other parties is allowed to the data in the server. The data are seen, mapped and cleaned by the Maastricht University admins in the iCARE4CVD project.

Copies of the data may send to other partners (such as Thomas Moore or Aachen University) who are in the data sharing agreement. This may be to further process the data (map, clean or analyse). When the data will be shared with other partners, Surf drive will be used to transfer them. This is a tool that is approved by Maastricht University.

The updated mappings will be saved in the cohort explorer and the data will be placed in the DCR once the data sharing agreement is signed by the consortium. The control to the data is given to the original data owner who should manage permissions on the data.

Annexes

Technical Factsheet

Bellow a technical summary of the architecture was provided by WP2 and send to all partners to understand the high-level work if WP2.

Having data is nice, but having useful data is essential!

WP1 and WP2 are closely collaborating to ensure that the consortium has access to useful and high-quality data. In WP1, we will curate relevant datasets and ensure they are ready to be used when our researchers need their questions answered. Data provided by members will be protected and only accessible by authorized individuals through the the multi-layered technical architecture built in WP2. The architecture will enable technical enforcement of the data management plan to facilitate compliance with data processing requirements.

A high-level overview of the target architecture

Our architecture has three components, each designed to protect patient data privacy while enabling flexible analysis (Fig. 1). LUCE Blockchain platform handles data permissions and holds data sharing agreements. The Cohort explorer UI based on knowledge graphs provides a unified interface for exploring cohorts on a meta-data level, making it easy for analysts to discover data. In the analysis layer, Decentriq Data Clean Rooms ensures secure data analysis while enabling regulatory compliance. Our architecture enables researchers to analyse data efficiently and securely while allowing partners providing data to maintain control over processing of such data and preserving patient privacy.

Figure 1. Technical Architecture Components

The user experience and implications

1. Users connect to the cohort explorer UI and create an account
2. They upload their data dictionary (metadata)
3. They get to the Decentriq environment where they get the encryption toolkit to connect their data to a Data Clean Room
4. Researchers form questions in the cohort explorer and analyse encrypted data in Data Clean Rooms
5. Data custodians approve the analyses.
6. Approved results are retrieved without the raw data ever being exposed or compromised.
7. Blockchain keeps an immutable track of everything that happened

For more information on the data protection and IT security implications please refer to [DCR Data Protection Whitepaper](#) or the [Joint Controllership Agreement](#)

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